

Gravitation : light cones, black holes and the equation of motion

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Abstract

The Painlevé - Gullstrand and the Schwarzschild metrics are reconsidered in connection with light cones and black hole predictions. A relativistic Newtonian formulation of gravitation where the fundamental role is played by the equivalence principle and Special Relativity is emphasized.

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1 Introduction

The impact Special Relativity (SR) [1] has had on our picture of the world can be hardly underestimated. However its message, to give a meaning to measurable quantities only, has been somewhat lost in General Relativity (GR) [2] due to the existence of different metrics, not always directly connected to measurable time and space intervals. For this reason we are going to reconsider the Painleve'- Gullstrand (P-G) [3] [4] and Schwarzschild (S) [5] metrics showing what are the same predictions and what not, and discuss the physical basis of one (P-G) , obtained independently of GR but based on the same original idea of Einstein that gravitation can be locally eliminated in the free fall frame (FFF) which represents therefore an equivalence principle (EP) inertial frame (EPIF). Therefore in these frames, which fall according to **Newton's law** [6] in terms of an **absolute time**, **SR** is manifestly valid. The only problem resides in expressing the infinitesimal displacement in the local system to that in external (global) coordinates. This implies an analogous relation for velocities.

2 The metrics

The Schwarzschild solution of GR for uncharged non rotating objects is given by the invariant interval

$$ds^2 = c^2(1 - v^2(r)/c^2) dt^2 - dr^2/(1 - v^2/c^2) - dx_{\perp}^2 \quad (1)$$

The effect of gravitation on the SR invariant interval $ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - dr^2$ is represented by the quantity

$$\epsilon = \frac{v^2(r)}{c^2} = \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} = R_S$$

Among alternative solutions (metrics) let us consider the P-G

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= c^2 dt^2 - (dr - v(r) dt)^2 - dx_{\perp}^2 = \\ &= c^2(1 - v^2(r)/c^2) dt^2 + 2v(r) dt dr - dr^2 - dx_{\perp}^2 \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

The two have been shown to be equivalent thanks to an ad hoc time transformation (see e.g. [7]).

However by this procedure one does not appreciate the interesting features of this metric, which is formulated in terms of **intrinsic coordinates in Euclidean space and proper time**. So in a sense this is "**the metric**" which follows more closely the SR requirements of attributing physical significance to measurable quantities only.

Let us determine the corresponding light cones. Their form contradicts previous results [7] [8] [9].

Light cones

Light velocity is obtained by setting to zero the corresponding invariant intervals. The velocity in directions orthogonal to the radius in the P-G metric as well as in the S takes the value

$$c_{\perp} = rd\theta/dt = c(1 - v^2/c^2)^{1/2}. \quad (3)$$

Along the radius, the velocity in the P-G metric is

$$c_r = dr/dt = \pm c - v(r), \quad (4)$$

which trivially satisfies the EP whereas in the S metric is

$$dr/dt = \pm c(1 - v^2/c^2) \quad (5)$$

So we see that *the S solution does not satisfy the EP.*

Some comments are in order to plot the previous expressions.

In the P-G metric where the cone radial opening remains constant and equal to $2c$ the cone simply rotates to the left for smaller radii so that (t,r) solutions are customarily plotted also inside the black hole. However the transverse component tends to zero, thus making the cones to become more and more squeezed in the transverse direction; below R_S this component becomes imaginary thus preventing inner solutions also in this metric. The previous argument is valid also for the S metric.

Therefore BHs, even in a standard formulation, remove the gravitational singularity of gravitation since they forbid the possibility of reaching the origin. It has to be underlined that also in this case is SR which cures the problem since it all depends on the presence on v^2/c^2 in the square root i.e. that **v cannot exceed c**.

This fact disposes in particular of the possibility of inverting below the Schwarzschild radius (t,r) coordinates, allowed by the consideration of the invariant interval only (in other words light cones are given by (t,r) and obviously not by (t^2, r^2)). Thus all related speculations are simply idle [9].

Light cones as a function of r in the Painlevé-Gullstrand and Schwarzschild metric respectively. A singularity at R_S only arises for the second metric but also in the P-G coordinates the transverse light component prevents inner light cones. Thus for a black hole no light can escape but also nothing could enter either !

The same result can be reached from energy conservation for a photon of energy ϵ in the gravitational field of a mass M the energy

$$\tilde{E} = \epsilon - \frac{GM\epsilon/c^2}{r} \quad (6)$$

The photon can thus reach infinity (zero total energy) if $\frac{GM}{c^2 r} = 1$

If $r < R_S = \frac{GM}{c^2}$ it cannot. ¹ Since the problem is time independent also the time reversed process is allowed and **photon can neither escape nor enter**.

This hypothesis asks for a consideration of the possibility of the reality of black holes (in this static picture : no matter accretion nor radiation) .

Indeed in both approaches the existence of a BH is related to the fact that the particle can reach the velocity of light without enquiring about the possible existence of the such a source.

In that respect

$$\frac{GM}{c^2 R} = 1 \quad (7)$$

is equivalent to

$$E = Mc^2 - \frac{GM^2}{R} = 0 \quad (8)$$

i.e. that the mass is completely swallowed by its self energy (this mechanism is already appreciable in neutron stars). Thus according to this argument a BH should exert no gravitational effect . This argument contradicts the picture [11] according to which there should be an accumulation of matter outside the BH because of its strong gravitational attraction, although we share the same conclusion about the inaccessibility of the interior.

The same conclusion has been reached in [12], ² where an alternative formulation has been presented.

Therefore within this framework (where a dimensional argument only is possible for the expression of the self energy) BHs do not exist. How can this be reconciled with what has been observed ? The point is that mass and radius are of course not known or defined with sufficient precision. Thus it is conceivable that the self energy does not completely compensate the mass so that a still strong attraction remains.

$$E' = Mc^2 - \delta\left(\frac{GM^2}{R}\right) \neq 0 \quad (9)$$

in such a way that we might be in the presence of a quasi BH (QBH, $\delta < 1$) or grey hole (GH) which might therefore still exert a considerable attraction.

Thus the concept of BH, taken at its face value, is just a formal result of our equations, with scant connection with reality.

¹This naive argument corrects the original Mitchel- Laplace one based on a non relativistic treatment of the kinetic energy of a particle of mass m yielding a wrong factor of 2 which enters the definition of the Schwarzschild radius. This is confirmed in the low energy treatment of GR which is inadequate for the Universe treatment. [10]

²An unfortunate misprint appears in Eq.(19). The round bracket in the denominator of the r.h.s. should instead appear in the numerator

3 Gravitation in the Lagrangian formulation

a) Newton's law

Classical Mechanics can be indeed formulated in terms of the principle of least action in inertial frames. The implementation of the EP in the non relativistic free Lagrangian $\mathcal{L} = m/2 \dot{r}^2$ is immediate. It is enough to express the velocity in the local EPIF or in other words to subtract the free fall velocity

$$\dot{r} \rightarrow \dot{r} - v(r)$$

The principle of least action for a particle in the presence of gravity is thus given by

$$\delta \int dt (m/2 [(\dot{r} - v(r))^2 + r^2(\dot{\theta})^2]) = 0. \quad (10)$$

The Lagrange equations yield for the radial coordinate

$$\begin{aligned} d/dt(\dot{r} - v(r)) + (\dot{r} - v(r))dv/dr - r(\dot{\theta})^2 = \\ = \ddot{r} - d/dr(1/2v^2(r)) - r(\dot{\theta})^2 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since $1/2 v^2(r) = GM/r$, the Newton's radial equation of motion is obtained

$$\ddot{r} = -GM/r^2 \quad (12)$$

and the same holds also for the angular variables. A constant v would only amount to a change of inertial frame. Notice how closely related are the EP and the equation of motion.

e) Relativistic Newton's law

The relativistic extension of the previous result is easily obtained in the same Lagrangian approach. The formulation of relativistic mechanics is straightforward via the EP, which only amounts to substitute stationarity of the Minkowski invariant interval in inertial frames with the same for invariant intervals in EPIFs. The corresponding action is therefore obtained, as in the non-relativistic case, by the substitution $\dot{r} \rightarrow \dot{r} - v(r)$

$$\delta A = \delta \int \mathcal{L} dt = \delta \int ds = \delta \int dt (mc^2) \sqrt{(1 - 1/c^2 [(\dot{r} - v(r))^2 + r^2(\dot{\theta})^2])} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The equation of motion are given by the corresponding Euler Lagrange equations [7]³ They are equivalent to the geodesic equations in the metric defined by the above invariant interval, i.e. in the P-G metric.

Both solve in fact the same variational problem, the ordinary geodesic equations being obtained from a parametrization of trajectories with the

³A misprint appears in Eq.(15) The correct equation is the above one.

proper time. Let us also mention that the use of proper times is inappropriate in the many body case, which amounts to say that relativistic Newtonian gravitation is non linear as General Relativity. Let us recall that the same principle of the variation of the action was used by Hilbert [13] for an alternative derivation of Einstein's equations.

Thus

$$\mathcal{L} = (mc^2)\sqrt{(1 - 1/c^2[(\dot{r} - v(r))^2 + r^2(\dot{\theta})^2])} \equiv G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (14)$$

since the "fundamental tests" of General Relativity being obtained [7] [8] equally well from the relativistic Newtonian Lagrangian. It is clear from the way these equations have been derived that the fundamental role is played by Newton's law, its relativistic corrections being trivially expressed in terms of the weak field parameter $\frac{GM}{c^2 r}$. Their exact and a bit complicated expression is crucial for the calculation of Mercury's perihelion. This parameter is obviously unrelated to the corresponding quantity which governs the Universe [10]. Let us also stress that the apparent instantaneous feature of Newton's law has been shown in the beautiful approach by Feynman [14] to result as a low energy limit of a relativistic treatment based on the energy conserving amplitude for the exchange of a graviton between energy momentum tensors. This parallels the analogous treatment by Fermi [15] for the Coulomb potential.

4 Conclusions: much ado about .. ?

The aim of the present paper has been to debunk wide spread misbeliefs about the reality of space deformation and the necessity of the accompanying mathematical complications of GR. ⁴ It has been shown that the same results can be obtained in a much simpler and more physically founded formalism, supporting the physical content of the P-G metric over the S one. Thus in a sense in the description of reality, SR has regained its fundamental role with respect to GR, the dynamics being essentially given just from Newton's law. The consideration of light velocity, as backed up also by self energy considerations, has questioned inferences upon black holes.

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⁴Thus the phrase by Wheeler "Matter tells space how to curve. Space tells matter how to move" represents just an appealing interpretation of GR equations, without physical reality. It has to be replaced by the humbler "in undistorted space just relativistic Newtonian dynamics does the job".

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